

Adducts of Thiothiazyl Bromide with Metal Bromides

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Thiothiazyl bromide forms 1:1 adducts with AlBr_3 , SbBr_3 , TeBr_4 , SnBr_4 and TiBr_4 . It also forms 2:1 adducts with TeBr_4 , SnBr_4 and TiBr_4 . The adducts have been characterized by UA and IR spectral data. It is further indicated that there is equilibrium of the type: $\text{MBr}_5 + \text{Br} \rightleftharpoons \text{MBr}_6^-$ ($\text{M} = \text{Te or Ti}$).

THIOTRITHIAZYL chloride forms adducts with Lewis acids^{1,2} and transition metal chlorides³. The nature of thiothiazyl bromide has, however, not been studied. To throw light on the bromide-ion donor character of thiothiazyl bromide, its adducts with bromide, acceptor metal bromides have been prepared and characterized.

Thiothiazyl bromide was prepared as described⁴. Metal bromides, prepared by reacting the metals with excess bromine, were purified before use. The adducts of thiothiazyl bromide with the metal bromides were prepared by mixing them in the required stoichiometric ratio in dichloromethane. The contents were magnetically stirred and the adducts formed were filtered in vacuum, washed with dichloromethane and finally dried in vacuo. The analytical data of the compounds is given in the Table.

structure (C_{2v} sym) both in the solid and in the solution phase⁹ and has an IR active absorption band at 220 cm^{-1} . An absorption band at 224 cm^{-1} in $\text{S}_4\text{N}_8\text{SbBr}_4$ may thus be due to SbBr_4^- anion and therefore the latter may have the same type of geometry as in $(\text{Bu}^n_4\text{N})\text{SbBr}_4$. The presence of S_4N_8^+ cation in $\text{S}_4\text{N}_8\text{AlBr}_4$ suggests indirectly the presence of AlBr_4^- anion in the compound. The infrared absorption bands of AlBr_4^- fall below 200 cm^{-1} and could not be observed.

Thiothiazyl bromide and tellurium(IV) bromide when mixed in dichloromethane in 1:1 and 2:1 molar ratios give complexes $\text{S}_4\text{N}_8\text{TeBr}_6$ and $(\text{S}_4\text{N}_8)_2\text{TeBr}_6$ respectively. The far IR spectrum of $(\text{S}_4\text{N}_8)_2\text{TeBr}_6$ shows an absorption band at 200 cm^{-1} , which may be attributed to $\nu\text{Te-Br}$. This band¹⁰ in K_2TeBr_6 and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{TeBr}_6$ occurs at 195 cm^{-1} . Tellurium(IV) halides usually form TeX_6^{2-} .

TABLE—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THIOTRITHIAZYL BROMIDE-METAL BROMIDE ADDUCTS.

Formula	Colour	Found %				Required %			
		S	Br	N	M*	S	Br	N	M*
$\text{S}_4\text{N}_8\text{AlBr}_4$	Light Brown	25.7	61.2	7.9	5.1	24.7	61.8	8.1	5.2
$\text{S}_4\text{N}_8\text{SnBr}_6$	Yellow	17.8	57.9	5.9	16.9	18.5	58.1	6.1	17.2
$(\text{S}_4\text{N}_8)_2\text{SnBr}_6$	Dark Yellow	26.9	50.7	8.7	12.1	27.2	51.1	8.9	12.6
$\text{S}_4\text{N}_8\text{TeBr}_6$	Orange	18.2	57.4	6.1	18.8	18.4	57.3	6.0	18.3
$(\text{S}_4\text{N}_8)_2\text{TeBr}_6$	Red	26.9	50.7	8.7	13.5	27.0	50.6	8.8	13.5
$\text{S}_4\text{N}_8\text{TiBr}_6$	Red	19.8	64.2	6.7	7.3	20.7	64.7	6.8	7.7
$(\text{S}_4\text{N}_8)_2\text{TiBr}_6$	Orange	28.9	54.8	9.6	5.2	29.5	55.3	9.7	5.5
$\text{S}_4\text{N}_8\text{SbBr}_4$	Orange Yellow	20.4	52.0	6.4	19.2	20.9	52.3	6.8	19.9

M* = Metal

Results and Discussion

Thiothiazyl bromide forms adducts, $\text{S}_4\text{N}_8\text{AlBr}_4$, $\text{S}_4\text{N}_8\text{SbBr}_4$, $\text{S}_4\text{N}_8\text{SnBr}_6$, $(\text{S}_4\text{N}_8)_2\text{SnBr}_6$, $\text{S}_4\text{N}_8\text{TeBr}_6$, $(\text{S}_4\text{N}_8)_2\text{TeBr}_6$, $\text{S}_4\text{N}_8\text{TiBr}_6$ and $(\text{S}_4\text{N}_8)_2\text{TiBr}_6$ with AlBr_3 , SbBr_3 , SnBr_4 , TeBr_4 and TiBr_4 respectively. The presence of the cation, S_4N_8^+ , in these adducts has been confirmed by its spot test⁵, prominent infrared absorption bands⁶ and also by observing their uv spectra^{7,8} in nujol mull.

Antimony(III) bromide and thiothiazyl bromide react in 1:1 molar ratio to give an orange yellow crystalline compound $\text{S}_4\text{N}_8\text{SbBr}_4$. The anion SbBr_4^- in $(\text{Bu}^n_4\text{N})\text{SbBr}_4$ has a distorted tetrahedral

anions, but there is an evidence for the presence of TeX_6^{2-} anions¹¹. Hence, the possibility of the presence of TeBr_5^- and TeBr_6^{2-} anions in these complexes may exist. Moreover, the interconversion of $(\text{S}_4\text{N}_8)\text{TeBr}_6$ to $(\text{S}_4\text{N}_8)_2\text{TeBr}_6$ and vice versa also supports the presence of these anions⁶.

Titanium(IV) and tin(IV) halides are known to form five or six coordinate complexes^{12,13}. Both tin(IV) and titanium(IV) bromides react in dichloromethane with $\text{S}_4\text{N}_8\text{Br}$ in appropriate stoichiometric ratios to give $\text{S}_4\text{N}_8\text{SnBr}_6$, $(\text{S}_4\text{N}_8)_2\text{SnBr}_6$, $\text{S}_4\text{N}_8\text{TiBr}_6$ and $(\text{S}_4\text{N}_8)_2\text{TiBr}_6^{2-}$ respectively. The IR bands for SnBr_6^{2-} and TiBr_6^{2-} , which fall below 200 cm^{-1} , could not be observed. However, the presence of

the cation indirectly throws light on the existence and the nature of the anions.

Thiotrithiazyl pentabromotitanate(V), $S_4N_3TiBr_5$, can be converted to thiotrithiazyl hexabromotitanate (IV), $(S_4N_3)_2TiBr_6$ by adding the requisite amount of S_4N_3Br . The conversion of $(S_4N_3)_2TiBr_6$ to $S_4N_3TiBr_5$ can be achieved by adding the requisite amount of $TiBr_4$. Both these conversions can be accomplished in dichloromethane medium. This interconversion also suggests the presence of $TiBr_5^-$ and $TiBr_6^{2-}$ anions.

Thus unambiguous presence of the cation and the available IR data of the anions in the above complexes suggests that thiotrithiazyl bromide is a good bromide ion donor.

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